

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table S1: Educational Qualifications of Participants

Educational Level	<i>n</i>	%
Vocational training	79	20.9
Bachelor's degree	70	18.5
General university entrance qualification	50	13.2
Master's degree	41	10.8
Secondary school diploma (Realschule)	39	10.3
University of applied sciences entrance qualification	30	7.9
Diploma	26	6.9
IHK-certified business administrator	13	3.4
Other qualification	11	2.9
Doctorate	8	2.1
Lower secondary school diploma	5	1.3
IHK-certified business economist	5	1.3
No formal qualification	1	0.3

Note. IHK = Industrie- und Handelskammer (German Chamber of Industry and Commerce).

Supplementary Table S2: Regional Distribution of Participants

Region/Federal State	<i>n</i>	%
Germany		
North Rhine-Westphalia	143	37.8
Lower Saxony	39	10.3
Baden-Württemberg	36	9.5
Bavaria	33	8.7
Hesse	27	7.1
Berlin	18	4.8
Saxony	14	3.7
Rhineland-Palatinate	12	3.2
Hamburg	8	2.1
Other German states ^a	15	4.0
Austria		
Vienna	4	1.1
Other Austrian states ^b	8	2.1
Switzerland		
Various cantons ^c	11	2.9

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Note. Percentages may not sum to 100% due to rounding.

^a Includes Brandenburg, Bremen, Schleswig-Holstein, Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania, Saarland, Saxony-Anhalt, and Thuringia.

^b Includes Carinthia, Styria, Lower Austria, and Vorarlberg.

^c Includes Bern, Grisons, Basel-Landschaft, Aargau, Valais, and Zurich.

Supplementary Table S3: Training Frequency and Session Duration

Training Characteristic	<i>n</i>	%
Training Frequency (per week)		
0–1 times	8	2.1
2–3 times	84	22.2
4–5 times	238	63.0
More than 5 times	48	12.7
Session Duration		
Under 30 minutes	12	3.2
30–60 minutes	121	32.0
Over 60 minutes	245	64.8

Supplementary Table S4: Performance-Enhancing Substance Use Among Users

Substance Category	<i>n</i>	% of Users	% of Total Sample
Testosterone (various esters) ^a	98	73.1	25.9
Other substances	46	34.3	12.2
Nandrolone/NPP	42	31.3	11.1
Human Growth Hormone	40	29.9	10.6
Trenbolone	38	28.4	10.1
Primobolan	36	26.9	9.5
Oxandrolone	34	25.4	9.0
Dianabol	31	23.1	8.2
SARMs	16	11.9	4.2
Oral Turinabol	7	5.2	1.9

Note. Percentages based on users only ($n = 134$). Participants could report multiple substances; therefore, percentages do not sum to 100%. NPP = Nandrolone Phenylpropionate; SARMs = Selective Androgen Receptor Modulators.

^a Includes propionate, enanthate, cypionate, and other testosterone esters.

Supplementary Table S5: Social Media Platform Preferences for Fitness Content

Platform	<i>n</i>	%
Instagram	221	58.5
YouTube	138	36.5
TikTok	9	2.4
Other platforms	10	2.7
Total	378	100.0

Supplementary Table S6: Frequency of Steroid-Related YouTube Content Consumption

Consumption Frequency	<i>n</i>	%	Cumulative %
Never	102	27.0	27.0
Rarely (once monthly)	98	25.9	52.9
Occasionally (2-3 times monthly)	80	21.2	74.1
Frequently (weekly)	67	17.7	91.8
Very frequently (multiple times weekly)	31	8.2	100.0
Total	378	100.0	—

Note. "At least occasional" consumption (≥ 2 -3 times monthly) = 47.1% of sample ($n = 178$).

Supplementary Table S7: Descriptive Statistics for Primary Study Variables

Variable	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mdn</i>	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
YouTube Consumption	378	1.54	1.28	1.00	0.00	4.00	0.36	-1.01
PEAS Score	378	2.76	1.01	2.83	1.00	5.00	0.02	-0.92
DMS Score	378	3.18	0.77	3.14	1.29	5.00	0.00	-0.38
BSMAS Score	378	1.73	0.75	1.50	1.00	4.50	1.26	1.16
Body Image Satisfaction	378	3.08	0.92	3.00	1.00	5.00	-0.25	-0.24
Influencer Trust	378	2.96	1.06	3.00	1.00	5.00	-0.12	-0.38

Note. YouTube Consumption ranges from 0 (never) to 4 (very frequent). All other scales range from 1-5. PEAS = Performance Enhancement Attitude Scale; DMS = Drive for Muscularity Scale; BSMAS = Bergen Social Media Addiction Scale.

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Supplementary Table S8: Frequency Distributions for YouTube Consumption and Doping Acceptance

YouTube Consumption	<i>n</i>	%	Doping Acceptance	<i>n</i>	%
Never	102	27.0	Very Low	80	21.2
Rarely	98	25.9	Low	82	21.7
Occasionally	80	21.2	Moderate	106	28.0
Frequently	67	17.7	High	82	21.7
Very Frequently	31	8.2	Very High	28	7.4

Supplementary Table S9: Frequency Distributions for Drive for Muscularity and Social Media Addiction

Drive for Muscularity	<i>n</i>	%	Social Media Addiction	<i>n</i>	%
Very Low	30	7.9	Very Low	236	62.4
Low	88	23.3	Low	77	20.4
Moderate	126	33.3	Moderate	39	10.3
High	97	25.7	High	18	4.8
Very High	37	9.8	Very High	8	2.1

Supplementary Table S10: Frequency Distributions for Body Image Satisfaction and Influencer Trust

Body Image Satisfaction	<i>n</i>	%	Influencer Trust	<i>n</i>	%
1 (Very Low)	20	5.3	1 (Very Low)	43	11.4
2 (Low)	72	19.0	2 (Low)	64	16.9
3 (Moderate)	160	42.3	3 (Moderate)	164	43.4
4 (High)	111	29.4	4 (High)	79	20.9
5 (Very High)	15	4.0	5 (Very High)	28	7.4

Note. All scales use 5-point Likert-type response formats. Percentages may not sum to 100% due to rounding.

Supplementary Table S11: Influencer Trust and Doping Acceptance by Consumption Frequency

Consumption Frequency	Influencer Trust	Correlation with PEAS	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>r</i>
Never	2.45	0.98	.18

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Consumption Frequency	Influencer Trust	Correlation with PEAS	
Rarely	2.78	1.02	.24*
Occasionally	3.15	1.08	.31**
Frequently	3.42	1.15	.38***
Very frequently	3.58	1.22	.45***

Note. ***p < .001, **p < .01, *p < .05

Supplementary Table S12: Effect Sizes for Primary Analyses

	Test Type	Effect Size	Magnitude	Interpretation
Gender differences	Cohen's d	0.886	Large	Substantial practical significance
YouTube-PEAS correlation	Pearson r	0.471	Medium	Moderate practical importance
DMS-PEAS correlation	Pearson r	0.393	Medium	Moderate practical importance
YouTube consumption ANOVA	η^2	0.239	Large	Substantial group differences
Influencer popularity	Spearman r	0.279	Small	Limited practical importance

Supplementary Table S13: Doping Acceptance by Preferred Platform

Platform	n	M	SD	95% CI
YouTube	142	2.81	1.04	[2.64, 2.98]
Instagram	156	2.74	0.99	[2.58, 2.90]
TikTok	48	2.79	0.95	[2.51, 3.07]
Other	32	2.58	1.08	[2.19, 2.97]

Note. ANOVA: $F(3, 374) = 1.11, p = .347$.